

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Bayesian inference of gene flow between sister lineages using genomic data

Yang, Z., Jiao, X., Cheng, S., and Zhu, T.

SI TEXT 1. BAYES FACTOR FOR THE TWO-SAMPLE TEST

Consider the two-sample test, in which samples are taken from two populations to test the equality of the population means with known variance. The data are $x_{ij} \sim N(\mu_i, 1)$, for $i = 1, 2$; $j = 1, \dots, n$. The null hypothesis is $H_0 : \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu$ while the alternative hypothesis is $H_1 : \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$. The constraint $\Omega_0 : \mu_1 = \mu_2$ reduces H_1 to H_0 . This test does not have any of the irregularities discussed in the paper. It is analytically tractable and serves to illustrate the S-D approach to calculating the Bayes factor and the use of reparametrization to deal with a null hypothesis formulated via equality constraints.

The data can be summarized as the two sample means, $\mathbf{x} = (\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2)$, with $\bar{x}_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_j x_{ij}$, $i = 1, 2$. As $\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2 \sim N(0, 2/n)$ under H_0 , the likelihood ratio test statistic is

$$2\Delta\ell = \frac{n}{2}(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2)^2, \quad (\text{S1})$$

to be compared with χ_1^2 .

For a Bayesian analysis, we assign the prior $\mu \sim N(0, 1/(2\tau))$ under H_0 , and the prior

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mu_1, \mu_2) &= \phi(\mu_1; 0, 1/\tau)\phi(\mu_2; 0, 1/\tau) \\ &= \frac{\tau}{2\pi} \exp\left\{-\frac{\tau}{2}(\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2)\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2})$$

under H_1 , with $\tau = 1$.

The posterior of parameters under H_1 is

$$p(\mu_1, \mu_2 | \mathbf{x}) = \phi\left(\mu_1; \frac{n\bar{x}_1}{\tau+n}, \frac{1}{\tau+n}\right)\phi\left(\mu_2; \frac{n\bar{x}_2}{\tau+n}, \frac{1}{\tau+n}\right). \quad (\text{S3})$$

The marginal likelihood is

$$\begin{aligned} m_0 &= p(\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2 | \Omega_0) \\ &= \int \phi(\mu; 0, \frac{1}{2\tau})\phi(\bar{x}_1; \mu, \frac{1}{n})\phi(\bar{x}_2; \mu, \frac{1}{n}) d\mu \\ &= \frac{n}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{\tau+n}} \exp\left\{\frac{n^2(\bar{x}_1 + \bar{x}_2)^2}{4(\tau+n)} - \frac{n(\bar{x}_1^2 + \bar{x}_2^2)}{2}\right\} \\ &= \frac{n}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{\tau+n}} \exp\left\{\frac{-n^2(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2)^2 - 2\tau n(\bar{x}_1^2 + \bar{x}_2^2)}{4(\tau+n)}\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S4})$$

under H_0 , and

$$\begin{aligned} m &= p(\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2) \\ &= \phi\left(\bar{x}_1; 0, \frac{1}{\tau} + \frac{1}{n}\right) \cdot \phi\left(\bar{x}_2; 0, \frac{1}{\tau} + \frac{1}{n}\right) \\ &= \frac{\tau n}{2\pi(\tau+n)} \exp\left\{-\frac{\tau n}{2(\tau+n)}(\bar{x}_1^2 + \bar{x}_2^2)\right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S5})$$

under H_1 . Thus the Bayes factor is

$$B_{10} = \frac{m}{m_0} = \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{\tau+n}} \exp\left\{\frac{n^2(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2)^2}{4(\tau+n)}\right\}. \quad (\text{S6})$$

Note that under H_0 , $\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2 \sim N(0, \frac{2}{n})$, so that for large n , the Bayes factor has the form $B_{10} \approx c \cdot n^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{\frac{1}{2}\chi^2}$, where $c = \sqrt{\tau}$ is a constant and χ^2 is a χ_1^2 variable. When H_0 is true, $B_{10} \rightarrow 0$ at the rate $n^{-\frac{1}{2}}$.

To apply the S-D density ratio, we re-parametrize H_1 so that $\theta' = (\mu_1, \delta)$, with $\delta = \mu_2 - \mu_1$. Then δ is the parameter of interest, with H_0 represented by $\delta = \delta_0 = 0$, while μ_1 is the nuisance parameter. The prior under H_1 is given by eq. S2 through a change of variables as

$$p(\mu_1, \delta) = \frac{1}{2\pi/\tau} \exp\left\{-\frac{\tau}{2}(\mu_1^2 + (\mu_1 + \delta)^2)\right\}. \quad (\text{S7})$$

The marginal prior for δ is

$$p(\delta) = \int p(\mu_1, \delta) d\mu_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi/\tau}} \exp\left\{-\frac{\tau}{4}\delta^2\right\} \quad (\text{S8})$$

or $\delta \sim N(0, 2/\tau)$.

To verify the condition on priors (eq. 1), note that from eq. S7 we have

$$p(\mu_1 | \delta) \propto e^{-\frac{\tau}{2}(2\mu_1^2 + 2\mu_1\delta)}, \quad (\text{S9})$$

or $p(\mu_1 | \delta) = \phi(\mu_1; -\delta/2, 1/(2\tau))$. Thus $p(\mu_1 | \delta_0) = \phi(\mu_1; 0, 1/(2\tau))$ under H_1 matches $p_0(\mu) = \phi(\mu; 0, 1/(2\tau))$ under H_0 , and the condition holds.

From eq. S3, μ_1, μ_2 are independent in the posterior. Thus δ has the posterior

$$p(\delta | \mathbf{x}) = \phi\left(\delta; \frac{n(\bar{x}_2 - \bar{x}_1)}{\tau+n}, \frac{2}{\tau+n}\right). \quad (\text{S10})$$

Using the prior and posterior of eqs. S8&S10, we get the Bayes factor via the S-D density ratio as

$$B_{10} = \frac{p(\delta_0)}{p(\delta_0 | \mathbf{x})} = \frac{\phi(0; 0, 2/\tau)}{\phi\left(0; \frac{n(\bar{x}_2 - \bar{x}_1)}{\tau+n}, \frac{2}{\tau+n}\right)}, \quad (\text{S11})$$

which simplifies to eq. S6.

Let (μ_{1i}, μ_{2i}) , $i = 1, \dots, N$ be a sample from the posterior under H_1 (e.g., generated from an MCMC algorithm). Define $\Omega_\epsilon : |\mu_1 - \mu_2| < \epsilon$ to be the *null region*, a strip along the diagonal line $\mu_1 = \mu_2$. Then

$$B_{10} \approx \frac{\mathbb{P}(\Omega_\epsilon)}{\mathbb{P}(\Omega_\epsilon | \mathbf{x})} = \frac{\mathbb{P}\{|\mu_1 - \mu_2| < \epsilon\}}{\mathbb{P}\{|\mu_1 - \mu_2| < \epsilon | \mathbf{x}\}}, \quad (\text{S12})$$

where $\mathbb{P}(\Omega_\epsilon | \mathbf{x})$ is the proportion of samples in which $|\mu_{1i} - \mu_{2i}| < \epsilon$. This should be $\approx p(\delta_0 | \mathbf{x}) \cdot 2\epsilon$, with $p(\delta_0 | \mathbf{x})$ from eq. S10. Similarly $\mathbb{P}(\Omega_\epsilon) = \mathbb{P}(|\mu_1 - \mu_2| < \epsilon) \approx p(\delta_0)2\epsilon$, with $p(\delta_0)$ from eq. S8. Thus $\mathbb{P}(\Omega_\epsilon)/\mathbb{P}(\Omega_\epsilon | \mathbf{x}) \approx p(\delta_0)/p(\delta_0 | \mathbf{x})$, which is eq. S11.

SI TEXT 2. THE S-D DENSITY RATIO FOR THE ONE-SAMPLE TEST AND THE BOREL-KOLMOGOROV PARADOX

Consider the one-sample test with unknown variance, in which a sample is taken to test $H_0 : N(0, \sigma^2)$ against $H_1 : N(\mu, \sigma^2)$, with σ^2 unknown. The parameter vector is $\theta_0 = (\sigma^2)$ under H_0 and $\theta = (\mu, \sigma^2)$ under H_1 . The data are an i.i.d. sample of size n , and may be summarized as the sample mean \bar{x} and variance $s^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2$, so that $\mathbf{x} = (\bar{x}, s^2)$. The likelihood functions under the two models are

$$\begin{aligned} L_0(\theta_0) &= (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-n/2} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} [n\bar{x}^2 + ns^2]\right\}, \\ L(\theta) &= (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-n/2} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} [n(\bar{x} - \mu)^2 + ns^2]\right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S13})$$

Under H_0 , we specify an inverse gamma prior, $\sigma^2 \sim \text{IG}(\alpha, \beta)$. Under H_1 , we let $\sigma^2 \sim \text{IG}(\alpha, \beta)$, and then given σ^2 , a Gaussian prior on μ , with $\mu|\sigma^2 \sim N(0, k\sigma^2)$ with k given, so that

$$p(\theta) = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} (\sigma^2)^{-\alpha-1} e^{-\beta/\sigma^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi k\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2k\sigma^2}\mu^2}. \quad (\text{S14})$$

The marginal likelihood values under H_0 and H_1 are

$$\begin{aligned} m_0 &= (2\beta)^\alpha \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \frac{n}{2})}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \pi^{-\frac{n}{2}} \left[2\beta + ns^2 + n\bar{x}^2\right]^{-\alpha - \frac{n}{2}}, \\ m &= (2\beta)^\alpha \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \frac{n}{2})}{\Gamma(\alpha)} (1 + nk)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \pi^{-\frac{n}{2}} \left[2\beta + ns^2 + \frac{n\bar{x}^2}{1 + nk}\right]^{-\alpha - \frac{n}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S15})$$

(O'Hagan and Forster, 2004, p.170).

The Bayes factor is

$$B = \frac{m}{m_0} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + nk}} \left[\frac{2\beta + ns^2 + n\bar{x}^2}{2\beta + ns^2 + \frac{n\bar{x}^2}{1 + nk}} \right]^{\alpha + \frac{n}{2}} \quad (\text{S16})$$

(O'Hagan and Forster, 2004, eq. 7.10; note that $\frac{a_1}{a_2}$ in the equation should be $\frac{a_2}{a_1}$)¹.

Note that under H_0 , $\frac{\bar{x}}{\sqrt{s^2/(n-1)}} \sim t_{n-1}$, the t distribution with $n-1$ degrees of freedom. Also $(1 + \frac{a}{n})^n \rightarrow e^a$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$. Thus for large n , t_{n-1} is approximately a $N(0, 1)$ variable, and the Bayes factor has the form $B_{10} \approx c \cdot n^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{\frac{1}{2}\chi^2}$, where $c = k^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is a constant and χ^2 is a χ^2_1 variable.

To apply the S-D approach, note that the conditional prior under H_1 is

$$p(\sigma^2|\mu = 0) \propto (\sigma^2)^{-\alpha-1-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\beta/\sigma^2}, \quad (\text{S17})$$

which is the density for $\text{IG}(\alpha + \frac{1}{2}, \beta)$. This does not match the prior $\sigma^2 \sim \text{IG}(\alpha, \beta)$ under H_0 .

¹In Example 7.3 of O'Hagan and Forster (2004, p.169-171), μ is assigned the prior $N(m, w\sigma^2)$ under H_1 but here we use $\mu \sim N(0, k\sigma^2)$, with the prior mean fixed at 0. Symbols in that Example correspond to those used here as follows: $w \rightarrow k$, $b \rightarrow 2\alpha$, $a \rightarrow 2\beta$, and $s^2 \rightarrow ns^2$, and the marginal likelihood values are $f_1(x) \rightarrow m$, and $f_2(x) \rightarrow m_0$, with $\frac{f_1(x)}{f_2(x)}$ in eq. 7.11 to be the Bayes factor $B = \frac{m}{m_0}$ here. We note a few typos in Example 7.3: in eq. 7.9, $(\mu - \bar{x})^2$ should be $n(\mu - \bar{x})^2$; in the equation for $f_1(x)$ on p.170, $\Gamma(b)$ should be $\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}b)$; and in eq. 7.10, $(\frac{a_1}{a_2})$ should be $(\frac{a_2}{a_1})$.

Now consider an alternative parametrization of H'_1 with $\theta' = (\zeta, \sigma^2)$ where $\zeta = \frac{\mu}{\sigma}$. The joint prior is given by eq. S14 as

$$p(\theta') = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} (\sigma^2)^{-\alpha-1} e^{-\beta/\sigma^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi k}} e^{-\frac{1}{2k}\zeta^2}, \quad (\text{S18})$$

which gives the conditional prior

$$p(\sigma^2|\zeta = 0) \propto (\sigma^2)^{-\alpha-1} e^{-\beta/\sigma^2}. \quad (\text{S19})$$

This is $\text{IG}(\alpha, \beta)$ and matches the prior under H_0 .

Thus conditioning on $\mu = 0$ and on $\zeta = \frac{\mu}{\sigma} = 0$ induces different distributions of σ^2 . Figure S1A&B show the μ - σ^2 plane for the prior $p(\mu, \sigma^2)$, and large values of σ^2 are clearly more common in the shaded area in B than in the shaded area in A. The conditioning event, $\zeta = \frac{\mu}{\sigma} = 0$, is somewhat informative about σ^2 , implying that σ^2 tends to be large.

To apply the S-D density ratio using ζ , note that the prior is $\pi(\zeta = 0) = (2\pi k)^{-1/2}$ and the posterior is

$$\pi(\zeta = 0|\mathbf{x}) = \sqrt{\frac{1 + nk}{2\pi k}} \left[\frac{2\beta + ns^2 + n\bar{x}^2}{2\beta + ns^2 + \frac{n\bar{x}^2}{1 + nk}} \right]^{-\alpha - \frac{n}{2}} \quad (\text{S20})$$

under H_1 (see Examples 1.6 & 7.3 in O'Hagan and Forster, 2004), so that the S-D ratio $B_\zeta = \frac{\pi(\zeta=0)}{\pi(\zeta=0|\mathbf{x})}$ gives B of eq. S16, as expected.

In contrast, with parameter μ in H_1 , we have

$$\pi(\mu = 0) = (2\pi k\beta)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \frac{1}{2})}{\Gamma(\alpha)}, \quad (\text{S21})$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(\mu = 0|\mathbf{x}) &= \left[1 + \frac{n^2 k \bar{x}^2}{(1 + nk)(2\beta + ns^2 + \frac{n\bar{x}^2}{1 + nk})} \right]^{-\alpha - \frac{n}{2}} \\ &\times \left[\frac{k}{1 + nk} (2\beta + ns^2 + n\bar{x}^2) \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\times \left[B\left(\frac{1}{2}, \alpha + \frac{n}{2}\right) \right]^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S22})$$

Thus the density ratio is

$$\begin{aligned} B_\mu &= \frac{\pi(\mu = 0)}{\pi(\mu = 0|\mathbf{x})} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + nk}} \left[1 + \frac{n^2 k \bar{x}^2}{(1 + nk)(2\beta + ns^2 + \frac{n\bar{x}^2}{1 + nk})} \right]^{\alpha + \frac{n}{2}} \\ &\times \sqrt{\frac{2\beta + ns^2 + n\bar{x}^2}{2\beta}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \frac{1}{2})}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \frac{n}{2})}{\Gamma(\alpha + \frac{n+1}{2})} \\ &= B \times c, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S23})$$

where c is the second factor in the product. Thus due to the mismatch of priors between models, $p(\sigma^2|H_0) \neq p(\sigma^2|\mu = 0, H_1)$, B_μ differs from the Bayes factor B (eq. S16) by the factor c .

REFERENCES

O'Hagan, A. and Forster, J. 2004. *Kendall's Advanced Theory of Statistics: Bayesian Inference*. Arnold, London.

Fig. S1: Illustration of the Borel-Kolmogorov paradox. Given the joint distribution $p(\mu, \sigma^2)$, $-\infty < \mu < \infty$, $0 < \sigma^2 < \infty$ (eq. S14, indicated by the contour lines), conditioning (A) on $\mu = 0$ and (B) on $\frac{\mu}{\sigma} = 0$ leads to different conditional distributions for σ^2 , with $p(\sigma^2|\mu = 0) \neq p(\sigma^2|\frac{\mu}{\sigma} = 0)$. Note that in each case the conditional distribution is the limiting distribution of σ^2 over the shaded area, when the size of the area approaches zero (i.e., when $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$).

Fig. S2: (A) Bayes factor for testing gene flow under the UDI model calculated using the S-D density ratio applied to the three segments (a, b, c) for the data of Figure 1F&G, plotted against the factor a for the prior standard deviation, so that $\epsilon_\varphi = \epsilon_\beta = a \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} = a \cdot 0.2886$, or $B_a = \frac{\epsilon_\varphi}{\mathbb{P}(\varphi < \epsilon_\varphi | x)}$, $B_b = \frac{\epsilon_\beta}{\mathbb{P}(1-\beta < \epsilon_\beta | x)}$, and $B_c = \frac{\epsilon_\varphi}{\mathbb{P}(1-\varphi < \epsilon_\varphi | x)}$, where $\beta = \tau_Y / \tau_R$. (B) Bayes factor for testing Gaussian mixture (eq. 29) for the data of figure 3D, plotted against the factor a , with the differentials given as $\epsilon_\alpha = a/\sqrt{12}$ and $\epsilon_\mu = a$.

Fig. S3: (A) Estimated posterior density for α in the Gaussian-mixture model of Figure 3A. For each dataset size n , a dataset is simulated under $H_0 : N(\mu, 1)$ with $\mu = 0.5$, and analyzed using MCMC under $H_1 : \alpha N(\mu_1, 1) + (1 - \alpha)N(\mu_2, 1)$ with the prior $\alpha \sim U(0, 1)$ and $\mu_1, \mu_2 \sim N(0, 1)$ (eq. 24). The density is symmetrical at $\alpha = 0.5$, and increasingly U-shaped with the increase of n . (B) Proportions of the subregions for the four datasets, $P_a + P_c = \mathbb{P}(\alpha < \epsilon_\alpha \cup 1 - \alpha < \epsilon_\alpha)$ and $P_\mu = \mathbb{P}(|\mu_1 - \mu_2| < \epsilon_\mu)$, with $\epsilon_\alpha = 0.01/\sqrt{12}$ and $\epsilon_\mu = 0.01$ (see eq. 28). (C, D) Box plots for posterior means of α and μ from 20 replicate datasets of size n simulated under H_0 . Sampled values of $\max(\alpha, 1 - \alpha)$ and $(\mu_1 + \mu_2)/2$ are used to calculate the posterior means in each dataset, but identification of parameters in H_1 is affected by label switching. (E, F) Boxplots of Bayes factors based on segments a&c (B_α) and b (B_μ) from the 20 replicates (see eq. 29). Note that $B \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Fig. S4: Trace plots and scattergrams for parameters under the UDI model (purple for τ_R , blue for τ_Y and red for φ (the 2nd y-axis) in analysis of the data of figure 1F&G under three priors, $\varphi \sim \text{Beta}(a, a)$, with (A) $a = \frac{1}{4}$, (B) $a = 1$, and (C) $a = 10$. Panel (B) is from figure 1. See legend to figure 1.

Fig. S5: Posterior means and 95% HPD CIs of parameters in BPP analysis of 100 replicate datasets simulated under H_0 : MSC (no gene flow) and analyzed under the MSC-I and MSC-M models. For MSC-I, both the UDI and BDI models are used. Results of Bayesian test of gene flow using those data are in table 3.

Fig. S6: The expected proportion of introgression under the MSC-M model (φ_0 , eq. 37).